

D3.1 Resilience Data Model Initial Version

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Flex4Res Members of Consortium

Table 0-1 Consortium Members

Partner name	Shortcode	Website link
PANEPISTIMIO PATRON	LMS	https://lms.mech.upatras.gr/
VOESTALPINE HIGH PERFORMANCE METALS DIGITAL SOLUTIONS GMBH	VOE	https://www.voestalpine.com/group/en/
SIDENOR VIOMICHANIKI CHALYVA ANONYMI ETAIRIA	SID	https://sidenor.gr/en/
HANS BERG GMBH&CO KG	HANS	https://www.berg-kg.de/de/
GOIMEK S COOP	GOI	https://www.goimek.com/es
SORALUCE S. COOP.	SOR	https://www.soraluce.com/en
EIT MANUFACTURING CENTRAL GGMBH	EITM	https://www.eitmanufacturing.eu/
NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	INTRA	https://www.netcompany-intrasoft.com/
CONTACT SOFTWARE GMBH	CONT	https://contact-software.com/
A1 DIGITAL INTERNATIONAL GMBH	A1	https://www.a1.digital/
BEIA	BEIA	https://beia.be/
SAVVY DATA SYSTEMS SL	SAV	https://www.savvydatasystems.com/es/inicio
MONDRAGON CORPORACION COOPERATIVA SCOOP	MON	https://www.mondragon-corporation.com/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	TU Wien (IFT)	http://www.ift.at/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT DARMSTADT	TUDa (PTW)	https://www.ptw.tu-darmstadt.de/
UNIVERSITAET SIEGEN	USI	https://www.uni-siegen.de/start/
IDEKO S COOP	IDE	https://www.ideko.es/

Table of Contents

Flex4Res Members of Consortium	2
Table of Contents	3
List of Tables	4
List of Abbreviations	4
Executive summary	5
1 Introduction.....	6
1.1 Motivation.....	6
1.2 Requirements.....	6
1.3 Solutions	6
2 Resilience Data Model	7
2.1 Approach.....	7
2.2 SIDENOR.....	8
2.3 Goimek.....	9
2.4 Voestalpine.....	9
2.5 Hans Berg.....	10
3 Conclusion and next steps	11
4 References	12
5 Appendix	13
5.1 Sidenor Data Model Entity Relationship Diagram	13
5.2 Goimek Data Model UML-Diagram	14
5.3 Voestalpine Data Model UML Diagram	15
5.4 Hans Berg Data Model UML Diagram.....	17

List of Tables

Table 0-1 Consortium Members	2
Table 0-1 List of abbreviations	4
Table 2-1 Sidenor Data Points	8
Table 2-2 Goimek data points	9
Table 2-3 Voestalpine data points	9
Table 2-4 Hans Berg data points	10

List of Abbreviations

Table 0-1 List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AAS	Asset Administration Shell
IDTA	International Digital Twin Association
UML	Unified Modelling Language
ERD	Entity Relationship Diagram

Executive summary

Deliverable 3.1 signifies a significant advancement within the Flex4Res project by introducing the initial version of the Resilience Data Model tailored for assessing resilience at macro, meso, and micro levels. The deliverable begins with a concise introduction, outlining its objectives and the necessary specifications for the data model. At the core of Deliverable 3.1 is the presentation of the inaugural Resilience Data Model, exemplified through four distinct use cases: Sidenor, Voestalpine, Goimek, and Hans Berg. Each use case contributes diverse data points and conditions to the data model, showcasing its adaptability for resilience assessment.

A subsequent summary highlights key achievements and contributions stemming from Deliverable 3.1, emphasizing the model's potential to simplify resilience assessment in a standardized manner across various organizational scales. Looking forward, the summary offers insights into the next steps of the project, presenting a roadmap for ongoing advancements.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Deliverable 3.1 emerges from the imperative within the Flex4Res project to establish a standardized framework for resilience assessment. Recognizing the inherent complexity of evaluating resilience across diverse use cases, the development of the Resilience Data Model is motivated by the need for a unified methodology. The primary purpose of Deliverable 3.1 is to introduce the foundational Resilience Data Model, serving as a common ground for evaluating resilience across tasks 3.2 and 3.3 within the project. This model is designed to be adaptable to the diverse conditions presented by use cases such as Sidenor, Voestalpine, Goimek, and Hansberg. Beyond its immediate application, Deliverable 3.1 lays the groundwork for future resilience assessment tasks within Flex4Res. The Resilience Data Model is positioned as a crucial foundation for standardized, scalable, and unbiased evaluations, contributing to the overarching success of the project.

1.2 Requirements

The Resilience Data Model in the Flex4Res project must meet specific requirements:

Hard Requirements:

- **Interoperability and Integrability:** The model must seamlessly integrate with AAS, OPC UA Companion Specifications, and Gaia-X Self-Description for compatibility while following the standards set by ISO/IEC 21823-1:2019-02 [1].
- **Scalability:** It should describe both static and dynamic relations among products, processes, resources, and digital services to handle complexity effectively.
- **Unified Ontology:** A common vocabulary and methods ensure standardized data representation for clarity and consistency.

Soft Requirements:

- **Penalty of Change Method:** The model should accommodate the Penalty of Change assessment methods, analyzing the impacts of changes within the value chain. [2]
- **Value Stream Resilience Assessment:** It must support Value Stream Resilience Assessment, enabling comprehensive evaluation of the value stream's ability to deliver value under varying conditions. [3]

1.3 Solutions

The proposed solution for the Resilience Data Model in the Flex4Res project combines three key elements to meet its objectives effectively:

1. **RDF Syntax with JSON-LD Serialization:** The Resilience Data Model adopts RDF syntax and utilizes JSON-LD serialization for structured and machine-readable data representation. This approach enhances data exchange and semantic interoperability.
2. **Knowledge Graph and Semantic Network:** Central to the solution is the implementation of a knowledge graph that serves as a semantic network. This structure facilitates the representation and organization of complex interrelationships among various entities. A database is integrated to ensure robust data storage and retrieval capabilities, enhancing the model's functionality.
3. **Collaboration with Industry Associations:** The development process involves close collaboration with industry organizations, including the Mechanical Engineering Industry Association (VDMA) and the Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA). This collaborative approach ensures a shared

understanding of project goals and requirements and promotes cross-sector usability. It aligns the model with industry best practices and standards.

2 Resilience Data Model

In this chapter, we present the initial version of the resilience data model employed within the Flex4Res project. We begin by outlining the methodology employed to arrive at this initial solution. Subsequently, the model is dissected into individual data points required for each specific use case.

2.1 Approach

In the development of the Flex4Res Resilience Data Model, insights, and methodologies from two related projects, DiNaPro and EuProGigant, were consolidated to create a robust foundation. Both projects faced analogous challenges and provided valuable input for shaping the initial and final versions of the data model.

DiNaPro:

DiNaPro, a German project, aimed to establish a standardized data model and data exchange format, essentially a digital twin, for assessing environmental sustainability in manufacturing. The project initially collaborated closely with a software service provider, employing user story mapping to identify initial data points. Subsequently, a unified data model was crafted with the OPC-UA companion specification as a reference. Challenges arose when not all partners readily adopted the standardized ontology and vocabulary. This was addressed by allowing partners to map the developed model to their models using a mapping array.

EuProGigant:

EuProGigant, a Gaia-X lighthouse project, and a Flex4Res partner, played a pivotal role in the development process. One significant milestone in EuProGigant's timeline was the creation of an information model for shopfloor data, encompassing a data model for a Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and machine process data. This data model was integrated into the Gaia-X self-description and utilized within the EuProGigant validation platform.

Drawing from the experiences of DiNaPro and EuProGigant, the methodological approach to create the Flex4Res Resilience Data Model is divided into four distinct steps, with the first two incorporated into the initial model in Deliverable 3.1 and the latter two in the final version:

1. *Gathering Data Points:* This initial step involves collecting existing data models present at the facilities of various use cases. Partners shared the data models they wished to utilize and further develop.
2. *Refining and Expanding Data Points:* Building upon the collected data models, this phase refines the collection by narrowing down the data points essential for resilience assessment. It also involves the addition of new data points required for the assessment. This process results in multiple submodels for each use case, containing the necessary data points and ontology for resilience assessment.
3. *Unifying Models:* The submodels, initially separate, are consolidated into three generic levels: macro, meso, and micro, utilizing a semantic network and knowledge graph. A unified vocabulary and ontology are established while ensuring scalability.
4. *Adherence to Interoperability Standards:* In the final step, the Resilience Data Model is shaped to meet interoperability requirements. Cross-validation with established standards such as AAS

models, OPC UA companion specifications, and the Gaia-X self-description is performed to ensure compliance.

In the following sections, we showcase the submodels for each use case in a tabular format, accompanied by Unified Modeling Language (UML) diagrams following the entity-relationship model format, which can be found in the appendices. The tables provide information on the data point's category, a brief description, and its standardization status. These results are a direct outcome of the initial two steps in our proposed methodology, and each data point plays a vital role in the resilience assessment.

2.2 SIDENOR

Within the scope of the use cases, Sidenor addresses both supply-chain and factory-level considerations. The submodel can be categorized into the following domains to represent Sidenor's data model:

Table 2-1 Sidenor Data Points

Datapoint	Description	Existing Standard/Submodel?
Time Series Data	Define time series for resilience assessment at supply chain and factory levels.	IDTA 02008-1-1 [4]
Resilience Data model	Diverse resilience assessments involving varying functions, probabilities, and scenarios.	--
Penalty	Information of different functions describing how the penalty will be computed.	--
Scenarios	Link different scenarios defined in the table scenario below.	--
Scenario	Creating a different scenario by linking different production parameters	--
Probability	Custom distribution of scenarios	--
Values	Values that are chained in a scenario, i.e., the scrap price.	--
Constrain	The constraints that a scenario may have.	--
Time Series Information	Information about different time series that will be used for the resilience assessment and to compute probabilities.	--
Time Series Information – has_ Time Series Data	This table is required to have many to many relations between the Time Series Information and the IDTA submodel Time Series Data.	--
Output	Different KPIs computed at the assessment and link them with a customer.	--

KPI	The KPI table aims to contain all the information about different KPIs resulting from the assessment.	--
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2.3 Goimek

Within the scope of the use cases, Goimek addresses the micro and meso-level considerations. To represent Goimek's data model, it can be categorized into the following domains:

Table 2-2 Goimek data points

Datapoint	Description	Existing Standard/Submodel?
Machine asset	Machine representation including critical components and technical description	IDTA 02003-1-2 [5] IDTA 02006-2-0 [6] IDTA 02008-1-1 [4]
MTTR	Average time to fix the component to normal operation after a failure	IDTA 02013-1-0 [7]
MTBF	Average operating time of the component between failures	IDTA 02013-1-0 [7]
FailureRate	Frequency of failures of the component in a given time interval. Usually expressed as a percentage.	--
RepairRate	Frequency of repairs of the component in a given time interval. Usually expressed as a percentage.	--
FailureCost	Associated cost of a component failure	--

2.4 Voestalpine

Similar to Goimek, Voestalpine addresses the meso-level considerations. To represent Voestalpine's data model, it can be categorized into the following domains:

Table 2-3 Voestalpine data points

Datapoint (Category)	Description	Existing Standard/Submodel?
Technical Data	Generic Frame for Technical Data for Industrial Equipment	IDTA 02003-1-2 [5]
Digital Nameplate	Digital Nameplate for Industrial Equipment	IDTA 02006-2-0 [6]
Time Series Data	A standardised way to represent time series data	IDTA 02008-1-1 [4]
Service Request Notification	Service Request Notification is a request for a service to be performed, such as maintenance, an inspection, or a return.	IDTA 02010-1-0 [8]

Company Hierarchy Structure	Metadata on the company's characteristics	--
Manufacturing Assets	Data on the machines as well as storage	--
Production Order	MES data	--
Tools	Information about used tools in machines	--

2.5 Hans Berg

Within the scope of the use cases, Hans Berg addresses the micro-level considerations. To represent Hans Berg's data model, it can be categorized into the following domains:

Table 2-4 Hans Berg data points

Datapoint (Category)	Description	Existing Standard/Submodel?
Company	Metadata on the company's characteristics	IDTA-02006-2-0 [6]
Manufacturing Tool	Meta information about used tools in machines	IDTA 02006-2-0 [6] IDTA-02008-1-1 [4] IDTA-02004-1-2 [9]
Machine Asset	Data on the machines	IDTA-02006-2-0 [6] IDTA-02003-1-2 [5]
Tool Part	Technological information about used tools in machines	--
Sensor System	Technological data of the press	--
Production Piece	Metadata on the workpiece	--
Production Material	Technological data on the workpiece	--
Production Order	MES Data	IDTA-02006-2-0 [6] IDTA-02002-1-0 [10]

3 Conclusion and next steps

Four use-case-specific submodels have been crafted as integral components of the Resilience Data Model. The subsequent phases, as outlined in the preceding chapter, involve the consolidation of these submodels into a standardized format, with provisions for the inclusion of additional data points. Following this, efforts will be directed towards implementing interoperability standards. The development of the Resilience Data Model aligns with the initiation of work package 5, coinciding with the commencement of the pilot use case. As part of this process, the finalized data model will undergo validation within the pilot use case, ensuring its suitability and effectiveness.

4 References

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5 Appendix

5.1 Sidenor Data Model Entity Relationship Diagram

5.2 Goimek Data Model UML-Diagram

5.3 Voestalpine Data Model UML Diagram

5.4 Hans Berg Data Model UML Diagram

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